

JUTE SEEDS.—*CORCHORUS OLITORIUS*. THE COMPOSITION OF OIL *OLITORIUS*. PART I

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The composition of fatty acids from the oil of *Corchorus olitorius* has been determined by fractionation of their methyl esters: palmitic acid, 15.65%; stearic acid, 4%; behenic acid, 1.66%; lignoceric acid, 1.12%; oleic acid, 12.43%; linoleic acid, 59.67%; C₂₀ (mono-ethenoid)-acid, 2.42%; and non-saponifiables, 3.05%.

Two varieties of Jute plant—*Corchorus capsularis* and *Corchorus olitorius*—are grown in Bengal. The seeds of the former are larger in size and of nut-brown in colour, while those of the latter are of a blue-black colour.

The analysis of the oil from *C. capsularis* was made by one of the authors (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 759) but a survey of literature reveals that no work has been done on the composition of the oil from the other variety of jute seeds—*C. olitorius*. It has been reported that the jute seed oil is largely used with satisfactory results by the natives of Hill Tippera, Bengal as a specific for skin diseases (Chowdhury, "Jute in Bengal", p. 48). The object of this investigation was to determine the constituents of a specimen of oil from *Corchorus olitorius*, in addition to making a study of the chemical composition of the seeds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Extraction of the Oil.—A sample of jute seeds (Chinsura Green) was obtained from the Director of Agricultural Research, Chinsura. These were dried in the sun, cleaned, and coarsely powdered. The powdered seeds were then completely extracted with petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°) in a soxhlet. The last trace of solvent naphtha was removed by heating on a water-bath under vacuum, yielding about 15% of a brownish yellow oil. In such extractions always freshly powdered seeds were employed as it was found that the powdered seeds on storage yielded oil with increasingly higher acid value. To compare the yield of oil by pressure, a sample of seeds was subjected to hydraulic pressure, but only 6-8% oil was obtained. The oil was darker in colour. The residual cake, when extracted with naphtha (b.p. 40°-60°), gave about 4-5% oil, thus showing a mechanical loss.

Characteristics of the Oil.—The naphtha-extracted oil was of brownish yellow colour which on refining became brighter. The freshly extracted oil had a characteristic odour which on keeping long gradually became musty and rancid. The oil on storing deposited some solid forming a dry adherent film at ordinary temperature. It burnt with a bright, odourless and almost non-sooty flame.

A specimen of the extracted oil was taken for analysis. The following* are some of the characteristics of the crude oil :

TABLE I

Moisture and other volatile matters	...	2.1%
Extraneous (non-fatty) impurities	...	10.5%
Total fatty matters	...	87.4%

Refining of the Oil.—In refining of the crude oil difficulty was experienced with the nature of alkali and other experimental conditions. Attempt to refine it with caustic soda solution was met with considerable loss on account of the difficulty in breaking up the emulsion once formed. The method with anhydrous sodium carbonate was also tried but the percentage of loss was still higher.

Since the loss in refining depends mainly upon the free fatty acid content of the oil, freshly extracted oil having low acid value from freshly powdered seeds was employed for refining. The following method of refining with magnesium oxide gave good results.

A lot of about 100 g. of the oil was thoroughly mixed up with about 0.5 g. of MgO, gently warmed on a water-bath for nearly 30 minutes and then kept in a vacuum desiccator for 24 hours. It was then warmed on a water-bath for a while and filtered hot and the filtrate extracted with ether. The solvent was distilled off and the residual oil was heated in a current of CO₂ at about 110° to remove the last trace of ether. About 86 g. of a light yellowish oil with an acid value of 1.4 was obtained.

The refined oil was used for the determination of the physical and chemical characteristics and compared with those of the crude oil.

TABLE II

	Refined oil.	Crude oil.		Refined oil	Crude oil	
Sp. gr (30°)	...	0.9184	0.9115	Acetyl value	19.8	...
Titer	...	—10°	...	R. M. value	0.21	...
Ref. index (30.2°)	...	1.4585	1.4605	Neutral oil content	96.4%	...
Sapon. value	...	191.7	190.9	Non-sap. (Kerr-Sorber)	3.05	3.27
Iodine number	...	103.3	107.7	Hehner value (insol. acid)	93.7%	...
Acid value	...	1.4	14.6	Glycerol	9.8	...

From the iodine value it is evident that the oil is a semi-drying one. The low R. M. value indicates that only a trace of glycerides of lower fatty acids is present, but high percentage of insoluble acid shows that a considerable amount of fixed fatty acids is present in the oil.

Saponification of the Oil.—On subjecting 250 g. of the oil to steam distillation the distillate was found to contain no volatile constituents.

The oil (250 g.) was saponified with a solution of 150 g. of KOH in about 600 ml. of alcohol (95-98%); the solution was boiled under reflux for 6 hours. The most of the alcohol was removed by distillation and the soap was dissolved in water. The unsaponifiable matter was separated from the soap solution with naphtha by the method of Jamieson. The naphtha extracts on complete removal of the solvent left some light yellowish mass (3%). On further crystallisation of this substance a white crystalline product was obtained. From preliminary examination this was found to contain a mixture of sterols. Their separation and further study will be discussed in a separate communication.

The mixed fatty acids were liberated from the residual soap solution by 10% sulphuric acid in presence of Congo red paper and extracted with ether. The ether

extract was washed several times till free from mineral acids, filtered, dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the solvent distilled off. The residual fatty acids were dried under vacuum at about 100° ; yield 93.68%.

Separation of Solid and Liquid Fatty Acids.—The mixed fatty acids were separated into solid (saturated) and liquid (unsaturated) acids and their iodine values determined. Two methods were tried and their comparative data are given in Table III. The operation was repeated till the solid acids showed minimum iodine value.

TABLE III

	Liquid acid.	Solid acid.
1 Twitchell lead-salt-alcohol method ...	78.0%	21.8% (I. No. 3.0)
2 Lead-salt-ether method ...	74.6%	25.3% (I. No. 16.3)

The solid fatty acids separated by Twitchell's method were practically free from unsaturated acids, as indicated by its iodine number and were used for further study.

Some characteristics of the mixed acids and the saturated and unsaturated acids were studied as shown below.

TABLE IV

	Mixed acid.	Unsatd. acid.	Satd. acid.
Melting point ...	...	..	$47^\circ\text{-}50^\circ$
Titer ...	$28.5^\circ\text{-}29.5^\circ$	-5°	...
Iodine number (Kaufmann)	119.1	148.5	3.0
Sap. value ...	201.7	198.2	213.5
Molecular wt. (mean)	277.6	282.5	262.3

Saturated Acids.—The solid fatty acids obtained by Twitchell's method were crystallised fractionally from 95% alcohol and kept overnight in a frigidaire whereby the least soluble fraction was obtained first in small amount, which melted at $72\text{-}74^\circ$ and had its neutralisation value 156.73. From this observation it was evident that some acids of higher carbon content than stearic acid were present. By applying Renard test for arachidic acid only a trace was detected.

From the mother-liquor major portion of the saturated acids was obtained by evaporating off the alcohol. This on further crystallisation from dilute alcohol yielded a product (m.p. $52^\circ\text{-}54^\circ$) having neutralisation value 212.4, which evidently showed that this major fraction of the saturated acids consisted of a mixture of palmitic and stearic acids forming a chemical entity which could not be further separated by fractional crystallisation. The saturated fatty acid constituents were, however, separated by fractionation of their methyl esters under vacuum.

Complete Fractionation Data for the Component Acids.—The oil yielded solid acid, 21.24%; liquid acid, 75.71% and N. S., 3.05%.

A sufficient quantity of methyl esters of both the solid and the liquid acids was prepared and the respective esters were fractionated through an E. H. P. column as described by Longenecker, (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1937, 56, 199T) under vacuum (0.2-0.5 mm.).

TABLE VA

Fractionation of methyl esters of solid acids.

Ester taken=21.79 g. (I. V. 2.9).

No.	Wt.	B.p.	S. E.	I. V.	Composition of ester fractions as saturated					
					C ₁₆	C ₁₈	C ₂₂	C ₂₄	C ₁₈	
S ₁	3.20 g.	148-152°	271.8	3.0	2.86	0.23	—	—	0.11	
S ₂	3.61	152-155°	273.1	3.5	2.82	0.65	—	—	0.14	
S ₃	4.10	155-160°	275.2	3.6	3.22	0.71	—	—	0.17	
S ₄	3.80	160-165°	278.3	4.2	2.58	1.04	—	—	0.18	
S ₅	3.91	165-168°	281.0	5.1	2.23	1.45	—	—	0.23	
S ₆	3.10	Residue	355.7	8.3	—	—	1.68	1.12	0.30	
					Weights :	13.71	4.08	1.68	1.12	1.13
					% Esters :	63.1	18.8	7.7	5.2	5.2
					% Acids :	63.0	18.8	7.8	5.3	5.1

TABLE VB

Fractionation of methyl esters of liquid acids.

Ester taken=32.70 g. (I. V. 144.3)

No.	Wt.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.	Composition of ester fractions				
					Saturated.	Unsaturated.			
					C ₁₈	C ₁₈ (mono).	C ₁₈ (di).	C ₂₀ (mono).	
L ₁	4.70 g.	140-145°	290.9	145.1	0.18	1.11	3.41	—	
L ₂	4.10	145-150°	291.1	149.0	0.14	0.81	3.15	—	
L ₃	5.31	150-158°	291.7	151.2	0.13	1.04	4.14	—	
L ₄	4.91	158-163°	292.0	153.1	0.16	0.76	3.59	—	
L ₅	4.39	163-170°	292.6	154.0	0.13	0.65	3.61	—	
L ₆	4.80	170-176°	293.1	156.1	0.19	0.51	4.10	—	
L ₇	4.40	Residue	300.2	147.7	0.08	—	3.28	1.04	
					Weights :	1.01	4.88	25.68	1.04
					% Esters :	3.1	14.9	78.8	3.2
					% Acids :	3.0	15.0	78.8	3.2

TABLE Vc

Calculated composition of total fatty acids from oil olitorius.

	Solid acids (21.24%).	Liquid acids (75.71%).	Total.
Saturated			
Palmitic	13.38	2.27	15.65
Stearic	4.00	—	4.00
Behenic	1.66	—	1.66
Lignoceric	1.12	—	1.12
Unsaturated			
Oleic	1.08	11.35	12.43
Linoleic etc.	—	59.67	59.67
C ₂₀ (mono-ethenoid)	—	2.42	2.42
Non-Saponifiables	—	—	3.05

Further investigations of the component glycerides and fatty acids of oil olitorius by the aid of the more recent techniques, such as spectrophotometric determination and low temperature crystallisation are being carried out by one of the authors (N. K. S.) in the laboratory of Prof. T. P. Hilditch, F. R.S. and will be the subject matter of a subsequent communication.

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